

Food region CoP's - a concept for collaboration to develop region-fit carbon farming for climate transition in agriculture systems

D1.5 "Joint strategy for EU collaboration and cluster development"

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Project CREDIBLE: “Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU”.

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Executive summary

In order to permeate widely in agrifood strategies, Carbon farming (CF) needs to embed comprehensively in sustainable transition in agrifood and forestry systems and tailored to local contexts. This is the message from Credible stakeholder dialogues and Carbon Farming Summits. To identify systemic transition pathways and efficient policies, local multi-actor collaborations which integrate the value chain, consider the local pedo-climatic and economic-policy context as well as specific capacities, are gaining recognition as platforms for incremental and integrated knowledge and learning.

This document builds on Deliverable 1.4 (Credible 2025) and embeds CF scheme development as one potential value from organized collaboration at regional level. It demonstrates how different sector and stakeholder objectives converge and can facilitate design of integrated governance solutions that enhance our joint capacities to adapt to and manage with the complexities and variations of context and scale. Also, it suggests how such collaboration can also create space for more effective financing flows from both public and private sources.

Fundamentally, this document presents a concept of Food Region Communities of Practice (CoP) for this purpose and outlines their multiple values. It further suggests how these should be operationalized and connected at EU level.

The document mainly targets rural communities, producers' collaborations and projects and initiatives operating in the agri-food, forestry and rural land use space and the connecting national and EU networks. The secondary target group is potential collaborators and facilitators such as business and finance sectors, EU programmes and authorities.

Whereas the activities and outcomes of the CREDIBLE Focus Group (FG) 1.5 were documented in Deliverable 1.4 (Credible 2025), this document incorporates stakeholder messages from further CREDIBLE interactions. The methodology used combines review of also academic, but mostly non-academic grey literature, online information, workshops, stakeholder dialogues and key informant interviews, including the authors' personal and institutional experience.

The overall message in this paper is, that, the Food Region CoP should be understood as an inclusive concept which links the values of both territorial and value system initiatives

and programs, can accelerate implementation of pilots catered to specific needs or issues and accelerate practice-policy transfer. The different functions of Food Region CoP's (presented in a table format in chapter 3.2) can be embedded as part of comprehensive landscape restoration programmes or the CoP's could evolve into such comprehensive territorial programmes over time.

Specifically, three contributions are highlighted from this paper:

- the Food Region CoP model incorporates the needs expressed by stakeholders with respect to CRCF implementation and with respect to a sustainable climate transition in agriculture and forestry;
- the Food Region CoP model can support co-creation and delivery of several concrete advances for systemic transition. These values manifest in context-adapted co-creation and piloting processes for various systemic elements supporting the transition for different functions, including farming and land management, agricultural advisory, producers' organisation, value chain management, finance, policy, CRCF scheme development and government level;
- based on existing examples and emerging concepts, three complementary strategies to build a sustainable financing base for regional food system collaboration are outlined: one driven by public funding, second driven by private and market involvement and the third building a case to attract capital investment.

The main contribution of the document for research and practice is to encourage research programmes and projects, in particular, within the EU Soil Mission and food and agriculture related partnerships, to engage with and link to local and regional development and practical projects and collaborations, and vice versa. This type of cross-fertilization and participatory research is increasingly valued also by EU authorities. Furthermore, the document recommends the local actors to use the Food Region CoP collaboration also as arenas for policy dialogue.

For policy, the messages are that i) more systematic collaboration at EU level and engagement of different governance levels for this type of regional collaboration is needed, and ii) recognition of the values and functions of such regional collaborations will advance learning and systemic transition.

Overall, region-based multi-actor collaboration offers multiple platforms and values to define and pilot systemic solutions and advance collective learning.

List of acronyms and abbreviations

AKIS	Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems
CF	Carbon Farming
CAP	EU Common Agricultural Policy
CRCF	Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Regulation
EC	European Commission
EIP	European Innovation Partnership(s)
LL	Living Lab
MAA	Multi-Actor Approach
MRV	Monitoring, Reporting and Verification (systems)
NRPP	National and Regional Partnership Plans
OG	Operational Group
ROI	Return-On-Investment

1. Project summary

This deliverable is part of the EU-funded project under the topic HORIZON-MISS-2022-SOIL-01-06, titled: Building momentum and trust to achieve credible soil carbon farming in the EU (project acronym: CREDIBLE, Grant Agreement #101112951).

The main goal of the CREDIBLE project is to build momentum and trust for the implementation of carbon farming in the EU. This will be primarily achieved by setting up and moderating a network of initiatives/projects/stakeholders for favouring transparency, environmental integrity, and methodology standardization in soil carbon accounting. Such a network will be responsible for pushing forward multiple discussions (articulated around three main themes: which practices; what standards; how to monitor) and is expected to evolve from a mostly technical/scientific network at the onset of the project, into a process catalysing policy making and business innovation toward its end. The transparent, open access, multi-actor dialogues required to build trust and co-create solutions will be orchestrated around three annual European Carbon Farming Summits, which will present opportunities for the network to interact with the broader stakeholder community and grow to the point it would attract further fundings for long term sustainability. Through the action, four specific objectives (SO) will be achieved:

SO1) to build and disseminate a practical toolbox for promoting carbon farming, capable of taking into account local land uses, best practices, and multi-actor interests;

SO2) to identify options for benchmarking and selecting standards, certification mechanisms, and policy instruments for carbon farming;

SO3) to favour the establishment of a network of soil carbon data collectors and repositories to improve measuring and monitoring carbon dynamics;

SO4) to build up processes and tools to drive conversations for the upscaling of carbon farming. CREDIBLE's ambition is to support the European Commission and the Expert Group on Carbon Removal in the identification and upscale of solutions for soil carbon farming. Tables 1 and 2 provide further information on the structure and composition of the project.

Table 1. CREDIBLE's work package structure

WP#	WP Name	Lead
WP1	Practical knowledge and fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development	11-BSAG
WP2	Navigating and selecting carbon standards and policy instruments	12-EEB
WP3	Existing monitoring capabilities as enablers of soil data collection and sharing	8 - UFZ
WP4	Networking and communication actions to drive Carbon Farming in the EU	15-CKIC
WP5	Project management and coordination	1 – SAE

Table 2. CREDIBLE's consortium composition

Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
Soluciones Agrícolas Ecoinnovadoras SL	SAE	ES
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	UCSC	IT
European Conservation Agriculture Federation	ECAF	BE
Association des Chambres d'Agriculture de l'Arc Atlantique	AC3A	FR
Greifswald University	UG	DE
Ecologic Institute	ECO	DE
European Association of Remote Sensing Companies	EARSC	BE
Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH	UFZ	DE
Centre de Recerca Ecològica i Aplicacions Forestals	CreAF	ES
Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de España U de coop sociedad cooperativa	COOP	ES

Baltic Sea Action Group	BSAG	FI
European Environmental Bureau	EEB	BE
European agroforestry federation	EURAF	FR
BioEconomy Cluster	BEC	SK
Climate KIC Foundation	CKIC	NL
University of Helsinki	UH	FI
Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food	ILVO	BE
Consiglio per la ricerca in agricoltura e l'analisi dell'economia agraria	CREA	IT
Agricultural Applications Private Company (AgroApps)	APPS	GR
Institute for Climate Economics	I4CE	FR
Ellinikos Georgikos Organismos - DIMITRA	ELGO	GR

2. Background: The converging paths

2.1 Fit-for-region carbon farming as sustainable transition path

2.1.1 Outcome of Credible dialogues and Carbon Farming Summits

One of the objectives of the CREDIBLE project, and WP1, in particular, was to guide carbon farming approaches to fit in the diverse regional contexts across Europe. This objective was validated by stakeholder input during the project, which emphasized regional-level adaptation of carbon farming (to environmental, structural, and policy contexts) as a pre-condition to its adoption and scaling. The input further pointed to aligning carbon farming with farm level productivity and management strategies. These preferences and lessons from collaborating clusters and experts were summarized in the 'Fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development' (Credible 2025, also: 'Fit-for-region blueprint'). As a way forward, the blueprint recommended utilizing participatory and collaborative models and structures that support territorial multi-actor collaboration (multi-actor approach, MAA).

On one hand, the synergies of carbon farming (CF) with climate resilience, and, on the other hand, the complex multi-level implementation pathways and structures justify to frame CF as a climate transition path based on fitting CF approaches to region level context and tapping into the potential and capacities of region and local level actors, initiatives and food chains. More specifically, there is an urge toward landscape level approaches that integrate biodiversity, water management, rural livelihoods, and ecosystem resilience. The messages from Carbon Farming Summits make a strong case for this. Stakeholders strongly view that CF cannot be scaled as a set of isolated practices but must be developed as an integrated ecosystem combining agronomy, data systems, finance and policy (Zimmer et al 2025a, Zimmer et al 2025b). Therefore, also policies and structures to scale and incentivize CF should be systemic and integrated beyond climate mitigation objectives. An operative example of this is Ireland applying a comprehensive, collaborative and adaptive strategy in this context, integrating CF and climate-related objectives with biodiversity and water quality targets (Department of Agriculture 2025).

This document builds on the 'Fit-for-region blueprint' (Credible 2025) and embeds CF scheme development as one potential opportunity from organizing collaboration at regional level. This document demonstrates how different sector and stakeholder

objectives converge and can facilitate design of integrated governance solutions that enhance our joint capacities to adapt to and manage with the complexities and variations of context and scale, while also creating space for more effective financing flows from both public and private sources.

2.1.2 Carbon farming and agricultural philosophies: growing interest in regenerative agriculture

Combining societal and private interests and specific environmental and economic objectives has led many stakeholders and advocates of sustainable food systems to turn interest in 'regenerative agriculture' as a model of agricultural production and land management that integrates public and private interests and objectives in a mutually beneficial way. This provides another strong impetus for a systems level approach, including attentiveness to the whole value chain (see i.a. LaCanne & Lundgren 2018). While this concept paper aims to convey an unbiased approach with respect to agricultural models¹, it does integrate biodiversity and water management considerations in agriculture and rural land use with climate mitigation and adaptation.

2.1.3 Cross-scale approach to serve multiple levels

Policymakers at national and EU levels stress the value of grassroots level information and the consequent need to convey context-specific experience and considerations to policy design. This can be translated also to reflect a 'learning-by-doing' approach which is adopted in the case of Ireland's carbon farming strategy and promoted by EU officials in context of the CRCF and other complex systemic challenges we are facing today. Also, it is proven that effective information and knowledge building among farmers rests on relatable examples and communication among peers (e.g. Ingram et al 2016). The benefits of a systemic (governance structures, value systems) approach also include consideration of sharing of risks, burden and benefits amongst the core actors, thereby supporting just transition. Working across scales, both spatial and temporal, as well as in terms of collective forms, allows to innovate approaches and solutions to facilitate systemic transition (see i.e. Aakkula et al 2006).

¹ Although the carbon farming concept is not limited to agriculture, but does cover also forestry, due to the methodology of relying on the practical and context-specific examples from the actors and networks close to CREDIBLE and the participating clusters, the conceptual collaboration model in this document is framed distinctively in agriculture and agri-food value chains. Yet, some relevant examples and references from forestry-related activities are included as they support the proposed approaches.

2.1.4 Move forward with connected territorial learning ecosystems

The 'Fit-for-region blueprint for carbon farming scheme development' put forth the idea that "pilot projects should be designed as learning ecosystems, where both practice and policy can evolve in tandem" (Credible 2025). Building on this idea, this document sees individual pilots as products that can emerge from true learning ecosystems and which provide lessons for the longer-term learning and adaptive management cycles that the ecosystems would support. This document introduces a concept to inspire and facilitate regional and landscape level collaborations and highlights the multiple values and opportunities for converging collaboration with different food system stakeholders. Converging synergies in objectives, stakeholder preferences and system functions, we aim to show how to get the full potential out of multi-actor collaboration and integration of objectives to develop context-specific and scalable systemic solutions for the holistically sustainable CF transition in agriculture. In that, it may also serve as a guidebook for projects and anyone currently operating or working in a multi-actor collaboration to identify issues and stakeholders to link to attract new collaborations, values and funding.

2.1.5 Approach and methodology

Whereas the activities and outcomes of the CREDIBLE Focus Group (FG) 1.5 were documented in Deliverable 1.4 (Credible 2025), this document builds on these and, incorporating stakeholder messages from further CREDIBLE interactions, outlines a concept for advancing CF in territorial multi-actor collaboration². The methodology used combines review of also academic, but mostly non-academic grey literature, online information, workshops, stakeholder dialogues, key informant interviews, as well as the authors' personal and institutional experience. The approach is not to report the process outcome, but to converge stakeholder observations and the thematic connections between the key CF related topics in a collaborative concept that could guide further action at local and EU levels.

2.2 Food region CoPs as an open concept for collaboration

This chapter outlines the concept of 'Food region Communities of Practice (CoP) (also: 'food regions', 'CoPs') and provides a definition to understand its relevance and value for

² Thereby reporting and fulfilling Credible-project Deliverable 1.5 'Joint strategy for EU collaboration and cluster development'.

scaling CF and the climate transition in the food system broadly. In acknowledgement that 'carbon farming' is not a concept well understood amongst farmers, nor is it a driving concept for the agri-food system actors, this document frames CF as part of sustainable climate transition approaches in primary production and the food system. Nevertheless, elements of CF and the CRCF are included as key components to consider and advance through the report.

2.2.1 Carbon farming transition and collaboration from the farmer's perspective

The Multi-Actor Approach (MAA) is already well established at conceptual level. This document suggests how it is turned into practical, working systems. A key insight from Carbon Farming Summit 2026 is that farmers do not adopt CF as an abstract concept, they adopt practical solutions that improve their farming systems. Financially rewarding carbon farming systems must integrate multiple components into a coherent business management framework that delivering increase in soil organic carbon (SOC), through farm level practices such as cover cropping or agroforestry, for agronomic as well as societal benefit. This shifts the entry point for collaboration. Rather than focusing on carbon as the primary objective, successful approaches frame CF through tangible benefits such as improved soil health, increased resilience to climate variability and enhanced economic performance. This shift requires aligning technical, economic and communication strategies with farmer realities, ensuring that carbon outcomes are integrated within broader agronomic and business improvements. As a result, effective CF systems are not built around isolated practices, but around integrated, farm level ecosystems that deliver multiple benefits along with climate action. From the farmers' perspective, essential elements in programmes that aim to accelerate farm level CF transition is qualified advisory and peer-support. In our approach, food regions and networks of food regions carry the properties to support such peer-exchange among farmers and advisors. In terms of results from agronomic research, farmers need more information about the combinations of measures within a cropping cycle or production system rather than results of the effects of individual measures.

2.2.2 Collaboration within the agri-food and forestry value systems

Sustainable CF strategies and the potential multiple cascading benefits strengthen the case for expanding collaboration beyond farmers, advisors and researchers. Increasingly, they must integrate actors from across the agri-food value chain, including companies,

financial institutions and carbon market players (e.g. Deloitte 2025, IRISCC 2026). This shift reflects the growing importance of linking farm level practices with corporate sustainability strategies, particularly in the context of GHG reduction. The ambition to deploy robust MRV under the Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming certification framework (CRCF) is aligned with these system needs. From this standpoint, integration of CF with scope 3 reporting (of emissions and sequestration) is particularly relevant. Also, biodiversity considerations and biodiversity-related indicators are increasingly adopted in corporate sustainability frameworks both in the agri-food, forestry and finance sectors (ICMA). This increases the demand for attributable, good quality data. Ideally, farm level data must connect to product level and value chain metrics, enabling its use across multiple purposes (i.a. IRISCC 2026). In the EU digitalization strategy, the principle of “collect once, use many times” (or 'Once-Only Principle; Cave et al 2017), underpins emerging data infrastructures in the agri-food sector. Data generated at farm level should be reusable across certification schemes, corporate reporting and policy frameworks. As a result, collaboration evolves into multi-level data ecosystems that connect farm practices with broader systems, including corporate reporting requirements, certification mechanisms and public policy objectives. Within this evolving landscape, the CRCF would benefit from linking with the data demands and infrastructures of the agri-food and forestry sector and develop structures in line with the industry's and producers' strategic objectives and needs. Access to relevant data is key to scaling climate and biodiversity action among the market actors, and the data needs of the CRCF and the MRV systems as well as the interlinkages with national inventories, scope 3 reporting and the CAP administration present strong arguments to develop integrated solutions that support multiple use (see IRISCC 2026).

2.2.3 Food region CoP's as an inclusive, thematic concept

The Community of Practice is an established concept in the scientific space and a concept which has restored and increased its value as a model acknowledged by the EU (JRC). This document, refraining from any critique on the existing definition, presents the Food Region CoP as a conceptual framing which is inclusive and aims to capture the multiple values from collaborative co-creation approaches embedded in research as well as more practice-oriented initiatives.

"Collaboration, co-creation with farmers and companies has helped research to take real world context into account and tailor solutions that make sense and are valuable to users and beneficiaries"

Jari Liski, Director of Climate Research,
Finnish Meteorological Institute, and
Scientific Director of Carbon Action collaboration

Credible dialogues have identified untapped potential in e.g. the EIP AGRI Operational Groups (regional collaborative groups with a specific purpose financed through the CAP, see CAP Network) and Soil Mission Living Labs as relevant multi-actor cluster structures to advance CF strategies. Also, the transformative value of comprehensive landscape approaches and landscape restoration programmes (LENs, Commonland, EIT FOOD landscape programme) has been noted. For system level adaptation and to support both territorial development and joint learning, multi-year programmes which have reinforced existing local organisations (or established new ones) and attracted funding from different sources on a continuous basis stand out as examples (e.g. AlVeIAI). Another example of the organic transitioning from carbon-focused initiative toward a more comprehensive value system level approach at local level is the Swedish Carbon Sequestration initiative which sees a future local climate transition path that may incorporate carbon credits as one vehicle for financing but which incorporates a multi-sector collaboration with attention to the farmer perspective, soil health and human capacity (Svensk Kolinlagring 2025).

While the incremental value from territorial, place-based collaboration is the distinctive feature of the CoP concept, this should integrate collaboration at other levels. Collaboration with the AKIS³ and research community more broadly does have its unique advantages. Experience from the Finnish Carbon Action multi-actor collaboration initiative has verified the value of cross-sector two-way collaboration and co-design, co-development. Similarly, farmer peer-groups and peer exchange can be valuable at any scale. In fact, it is more likely and effective to find connections between farmers that share a common problem, objective or a mindset, regardless of geographic proximity. The essence in multi-actor collaboration is to identify specific needs and design and adapt

³ “Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) are combined organisation and knowledge flows between individuals, organisations, and institutions who use and produce knowledge for agriculture and interrelated fields. ... Each EU Member State must outline its AKIS strategy within its CAP Strategic Plan, which is implemented through specific CAP interventions aimed at promoting knowledge exchange and innovation, including innovation-related activities of CAP Networks and EIP-AGRI Operational Groups” (DG AGRI 2026; see also CAP Network).

solutions which work in the contexts and respond to the multiple needs, to make them relevant, value added and scalable.

In summary, the Food Region CoP should be understood as an inclusive concept which links the values of both territorial and value system initiatives and programs, can accelerate implementation of pilots catered to specific needs or issues and accelerate practice-policy transfer. The different functions of food region CoP's (to be discussed in the next chapter) can be embedded as part of comprehensive landscape restoration programmes or the CoP's could evolve into such comprehensive territorial programs over time.

Chapters 4 and 5 discuss how the concept and action could be operationalized, how the EU level could facilitate cumulative learning and value of the CoPs and how the CoPs could be used for policy dialogue to increase policymakers' awareness and understanding of integrated and system level solutions.

3. Value system collaboration at region and landscape levels

3.1 From sector objectives to converging entry points and multiple functions

Agriculture, food production, rural land management and the food system are key operations with significant leveraging power in climate transition – reduction of emissions and increasing nature-based carbon sequestration. To scale CF in agricultural systems around the EU, there is a need to

- adopt an integrated approach on policy agendas and measures across agricultural policy, climate policy, corporate sustainability policy and sustainable financing;
- design compatible and complementary incentive measures for farm-level climate transition through the CAP and CRCF, responsive to farm level and land-owner needs and interests;
- deploy high-standard, cost-efficient and integrated MRV which can serve multiple end-uses; and
- facilitate learning at territorial and value chain levels, focusing on local priorities and deploying local capacities.

Additionally, the key actors and stakeholders would benefit from access to:

- ✓ established local stakeholder networks and sites for co-creation and demonstration and validation (MRV, industry)
- ✓ a benchmark MRV with demonstrated applicability in different environments (CRCF scheme developers, authorities, industry)
- ✓ reliable and attributable assessments about the effects of different crop rotations and land management approaches on soil carbon (farmers, carbon certificate schemes)
- ✓ value chain connections to develop use cases for the development of agri-data architecture, incl. data collection, data sharing, interfaces, repositories, registries (data owners, data producers, data users, data service providers)
- ✓ communication channels and support to build understanding on CF and explore closer peer organization (farmers)

Widely accepted understanding of the existing bottlenecks and needs in transitioning to and scaling future-proof agriculture systems point to the need to address these on the

context specific level, regionally, locally and through the value chains. Such systemic collaboration could increase collective capacity to i) develop agriculture and forestry systems in line with rural development, biodiversity and water quality objectives, ii) deploy performance monitoring frameworks to enable rewards/payments based on accurate, attributable and contextual data, and iii) involve the private sector in managing the public goods that it depends on and contributing to public benefits and positive societal outcomes.

3.2 Sector and function specific value of Food Region CoPs

The Food Region Community-of-Practice concept introduced here is based on identification of synergies between carbon farming and agri-food value chain strategies and drivers and enablers of the systemic climate transition. **Table 3** below summarizes the functions, values and arguments for system level, territorially bound multi-actor collaborations for the needed of agri-food & forestry adaptations. It highlights joint benefits in a pragmatic way, thereby suggesting connecting topics and values in place-based collaborations to advance learning and transition. Issues in operationalization, financing as well as upscaling and policy value are further discussed in Chapters 4 and 5.

Table 3. Identified potential values from Food Region CoP's

CoP action and potential benefit	Justification
Farming and land management	
<p>Optimizing crop rotations for multiple objectives (food production, soil health, climate resilience);</p> <p>Facilitating research to fill gaps with regards to impacts at rotation level.</p>	<p>Sustainable CF strategies integrate sustainable production strategies. Farmers need relatable examples and opportunities to experiment. Territorial level programs allow to study cumulative effects and research benefits from participatory elements.</p>
<p>Addressing land stewardship in landowner-farmer contracts, exploring solutions to overcome the barrier with rented farmland (as opposed to farmer-owned land) with regards to long-term soil health and CF strategies.</p>	<p>Rental lands and owner-operated farmland are subject to different considerations and judgements as regards long-term investment in soil health (see i.a. Stevens 2022). A needed structural solution could emerge through joint structures, organisation at landscape level, joint ventures or through administrative solutions or market standards that incorporate soil health and productivity and sustainability investments in farmland value. See also below under 'Finance'.</p>
<p>Addressing integrated infrastructure investment needs. Incorporate holistic drainage management and investments at collective level in local CF strategies.</p>	<p>Working drainage infrastructure is a prerequisite to sustainable CF strategies and cropping cycles. Optimally,</p>

	field drainage connects with landscape and catchment level water management.
Exploring farm and landscape management for shared co-benefits across sectors and value chain. Adapting actions to maximize co-benefits e.g. for biodiversity and water quality and water resources.	Connections with ecosystem service markets could be identified and optimally these could provide financial risk mitigation pathways for farmers. Natural water retention measures (NWRM) support landscape level carbon sequestration and biodiversity.
Building monitoring and verification capacity on co-benefits.	Currently, reduction of chemicals (for biodiversity benefit) and GHG are the only criteria applied for agriculture in sustainability-linked loan monitoring framework (ICMA). Data gaps hinder biodiversity investments and rewarding farmers for beneficial practices or outcomes. Local initiatives with local expertise and capacity can help address data gaps locally and globally and develop new metrics and proxies. Shared data for steering agricultural transition across the value system and transparency at needed scales would facilitate also landscape and watershed level attribution of outcomes and thereby steering and incentivization of landscape restoration programs (see i.a. EARA 2025).
Agricultural advisory	
Connecting place-based projects and action with AKIS and advisory services to build advisory capacities and group services to integrate soil and water management, CF and productivity.	CF measures need to be tailored and soil and water management expertise is important in adapting sustainable CF strategies at farm level. Group approaches improve farmers' possibilities to join CF certification projects.
Producers' organisation	
Developing and strengthening producers' organisation. Initiate and support local and thematic peer groups and communities. Explore Art. 210a of the Common Market Organisation Regulation (CMO) as enabler of incremental environmental strategies/investments/considerations.	Top-down climate programmes (by food industry) or CRCF schemes driven by maximal soil carbon sequestration (or emission mitigation) may leave farmers in a subordinated market position with little room for adaptation for farm-level resilience and sustainability strategies. There are also risks that such schemes will not produce positive impacts at scale. Stronger producer organisation would strengthen farmers position in the carbon (markets), landscape collaborations and yield more sustainable strategies and outcomes.
Food industry	
Co-development of supply chain management, industry criteria and incentive frameworks, including public food procurement criteria. Landscape/territorial approaches and schemes for agriculture (or "agri-CULTURE") and supply chain.	Sustainability frameworks e.g. for regenerative agriculture are developing but need to align and improve practical implementability and MRV. Adopting a continuous improvement approach in longer-term programs (e.g. SAI Platform) aligns with farm level adaptation and transition as well as with the life span of also CF projects thus

<p>Exploring the role of food processors as levers for change.</p>	<p>facilitating branding the region for CF schemes. Territories could use local food and scientific capacities as a strength to address local environment issues and develop value chains (e.g. Emilia Romagna, Italy).</p>
<p>Monetization of data-based value for farmers, through building capacity to attribute action to impact with right data or applicable proxies.</p> <p>Building equitable data strategies and solutions with farmers retaining ownership of their data and exploring payments for data provision as an alternative to other forms of payments in a controlled environment.</p>	<p>Trust between farmers and the rest of the value system and society concerning data and data use is critical to advances in data-based valuation and innovations to support transition (i.a. IRISCC 2026). At regional and local level, benefits are tangible for the community and stakeholders and more easily valued in the market.</p>
<p>Addressing data needs of the whole value system (food companies, banks, authorities), developing joint metrics and shared use.</p> <p>Reconciliation of variabilities in scale (area-based vs crop-based) and defining MRV needs.</p>	<p>Banks, food companies and global industry frameworks support data sharing as well as focus on outcome metrics, monitoring of effects and trends and emphasizing remote sensing over human-dependent reporting (e.g. Carbon Action 2026).</p> <p>Identification of impact metrics at landscape or wider territorial scale beyond single farm relevant for the value chain may lead to innovations in information-based management and policy that are more cost-efficient, scalable and comprehensive.</p> <p>Carbon Action MRV (Sentinel 2-Yasso) has been demonstrated to serve both food industry ESG and GHG protocol reporting, CRCF and national inventories (Vira et al 2025), also Liski 2025). In landscape CoPs, joint MRV could be an anchor to develop joint data solutions.</p>
<p>Developing use cases and proofs of concept for data transfer along the value chain (e.g. digital product passport).</p> <p>Designing and piloting joint data structures and data spaces in agri-food value chain at territorial level, and to link agri-food and CRCF.</p>	<p>Multi-actor collaborations can make data collection more cost efficient.</p> <p>Certain regions or MS have attributes (such as unique Field ID registry as in Finland) are more ready to develop data-driven solutions, landscape and territorial approaches can accelerate these as EU pilots. Place-based collaboration can support convening motivated multi-actor groups to experiment in real-world context (IRISCC 2026).</p>
<p>Finance</p>	
<p>Development of measures and metrics with commercial banks for agricultural credits to support climate resilience and transition (validation of measures, methods to monetize (collateral) value of farmland agronomic quality attributes).</p>	<p>Banking sector has climate targets and GHG per e.g. agricultural product portfolio is reported. Climate change increases the banks credit risk as well as wider contagious risk in the market (EEA 2024). There is incentive both to improve economic prospects of lenders and rural communities, as well as to convert loans to sustainability-linked loans (see further de Wit 2025). Lenders monitor per target indicators and credit conditions can be changed based on a verified path to target (personal</p>

	<p>communication; Console 2022). A clear public framework for "coherence, credibility and accessibility" is needed for sustainability-linked instruments and indicators (EESC 2025, Tchoukanov 2025).</p>
<p>Exploring coordinated deployment of finance-linked incentive and reward schemes.</p>	<p>The value of local / territorial value chain collaborations for innovating finance solutions has been proven i.a. by regional Living Labs on CF. These demonstrate ability to involve agrifood and banking stakeholders in dialogue on systemic financing, advocating i.a. the need for innovative blended finance and risk-sharing mechanisms and participatory approaches "as essential to improving system bankability" (Zibecchi, 2025). Food chain actors' position and contract conditions with respect to agricultural producers create hindrances to sustainability which cannot only be solved by publicly funded programmes (i.a. IEEP 2022).</p>
<p>Innovation of financing and risk sharing arrangements, especially for integrated regionally tailored programmes and CF schemes, to mitigate funding gaps (both with respect to needed practices as well as to bridge transition) and demonstrate the impact of finance beyond single farm scale.</p> <p>Development of public private blended funding models, bonds landscape funding, collective investments, as well as combinations of new insurance schemes, sustainability-linked loans and large-scale green investments.</p>	<p>Rethinking and reconfiguring finance (credit), investment, incentive, risk management and public programmes is needed to stimulate transformative change in agriculture. The perceived climate risk which, through the system affects farmers negatively, needs to be turned around to demonstrate how right farming practises can mitigate the risk and strengthen the creditors position (i.a. EARA 2025).</p> <p>"Valley of death" in CF and regenerative farming transition underlines the need for support and security over the initial transition years. Coordinated, systemic territorial or value chain collaborations may also be able to attract so-called 'patient capital' (Deeg & Hardie 2016) that accepts a longer time scale in returns, as the investments strategies for patient capital values sustainability, but still expects tangible impact and economic return.</p>
<p>Attracting global risk capital to systemic regional development and value chain initiatives.</p>	<p>Global risk capital seeks investable projects at sufficiently large scale with clear metrics and monitoring to attribute investment to impact and measure the value of the investment (ROI). In short, there must be a 'business case' and expected profit. Coordinated landscapes/regions can be equipped with attributes that cater to investment considerations. These include: aggregation of land managers, shared MRV systems, risk pooling and permanence mechanisms, integration with value chains and ESG measures, delivery of landscape-scale co-benefits, and alignment with public funding frameworks (i.a. Deloitte 2025).</p>
<p>Tailoring insurance to serve as a lever for sustainability and to incentivize and reward for sustainable land management, climate transition and investments, for</p>	<p>Financial safeguards for farmers do not offer incentives for adaptation & transformation. There is a need for regulatory push to make insurance schemes also to incentivize</p>

<p>regional climate strategies (parametric, index-based insurance).</p> <p>Innovating insurance schemes, e.g. transition insurance schemes in public-private partnerships involving agricultural banks, insurers, off-takers, authorities.</p> <p>Exploring ways to link insurance with new green/sustainability-linked loans and forms of guarantees for these.</p>	<p>transition and climate adaptation (EARA 2025, EESC 2025, Bucheli et al 2023).</p> <p>Parametric insurance is implicitly area-based as triggers and parameters are defined and monitored territorially. Locally based, participatory co-design is particularly valuable and suitable to develop parametric insurance. Public-private partnerships can accelerate market demand and improve economic sustainability from business and societal perspective, incorporation in regional strategic planning may provide additional lever for climate contingency measures and investments (Berninger et al 2026).</p>
<p>Policy</p>	
<p>CAP 2028-2034:</p> <p>Testing performance-based indicators with farmers in a given context, aligned with farm subsidy programmes.</p> <p>Increasing knowledge of the impact of CAP on farm management strategies, investment decisions, land valuation and transition strategies.</p> <p>Co-development of integrated regional plans for the NRPP.</p>	<p>Short term and long-term performance indicators facilitate policy alignment "financial mechanisms, regulatory frameworks and supply chains standards" (EESC 2025).</p> <p>Extensive government support helps most farms stay afloat and disincentivizes intangible investments in productivity and farming preconditions. As attention is on the financial sheets, not in what generates the profit for the farm, this also weakens resilience (personal communication).</p> <p>Regional pilots, e.g. for result-based CAP payments, supported by advisory (and possible market and organisational approaches, see above) yield information on data and MRV needs, implementability and impacts of the measure if implemented systematically. Refer to Attachment 2 for a pilot concept for a result-based CAP payment with multiple values-added from region-focused implementation.</p>
<p>CRCF:</p> <p>Development of regionally anchored and referenced national/regional strategies and capacities to benefit from carbon removal and CF certification and carbon markets.</p>	<p>As an emerging and evolving framework, the CRCF needs to be proven in practice and conducive local contexts need to emerge to attract carbon schemes and carbon market actors. Tapping into specific capacities and attributes, the MS and regions could organize as front-line "markets" for the CRCF.</p>
<p>CRCF schemes</p>	
<p>Aggregation of farms and hectares into projectable and investable projects and linking to group advisory.</p> <p>Streamlining MRV, testing standardized baselines.</p> <p>Concretizing and validating co-benefit criteria.</p> <p>Aligning schemes with value chain strategies and food industry programmes.</p>	<p>Territorial approach increases efficiency (and sometimes accuracy) of MRV (see i.a. Deloitte 2025), and the likelihood and real value of co-benefits. Regionally established standardized baseline benchmarks pave way to transition to standardized baselines as the European level norm.</p> <p>Incorporation of the value chain in regional CRCF schemes boosts demand from local level and offers</p>

	opportunities through pricing (see i.a. Deloitte 2025, IRISCC 2026).
Government (regional and municipal)	
<p>Integrated and co-coordinated regional climate, economic and rural strategies. Deployment a whole palette of tools to support these, including financial support to agriculture, insurance schemes, targeted advisory, public procurement.</p> <p>Linking CRCF schemes, agri-food sector GHG-mitigation strategies and regional strategies, to strengthen the value and utility of (CRCF) projects for local climate action and development</p> <p>Informational support and common spaces for dialogue for primary producers, land managers, value chain and support services.</p>	<p>Greater collaboration between producers, processors, and distributors can facilitate widespread integration of CF practices, delivering both economic and environmental benefits along the entire value chain of agricultural and food products. CF can be a driving feature as part of a broader rural development strategy and food system transition (Department of Agriculture 2025, Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council 2026). Regional authorities can "get the ball rolling", group [CF] projects, align with supply chain cooperation and tailor to regional needs and strategies (CoR 2023).</p>
Government (national)	
<p>Testing incremental targeted financial support and technical assistance to fill funding gaps in local climate action, climate transition and CRCF schemes that will not be covered by the market or external investors.</p> <p>Piloting result-based payments and utilizing as a resource for policy innovations and policy and social learning).</p> <p>Evaluation of climate objectives and accounting and mining knowledge for more effective climate policy plans.</p>	<p>Government involvement and public financial support is key in CF and transition strategies. National and regional CF initiatives (e.g. Belgium, Ireland, Italy) are government-anchored and validate strong public sector role. Publicly funded guarantees etc. can be difference-makers in transition schemes, result-based payments and in attracting capital investment. The regional context, with similar pedo-climatic conditions and agricultural structure and production serves testing result-based payments especially when the performance and payment need a baseline or reference (see i.a. EESC 2025) and can benefit from coordinated regional or local farming strategies and farm advisory and data infrastructures.</p> <p>Contextual multidimensional learning can help discover ways to incentivize to direct more market capital to climate measures in agriculture, forestry and rural land use.</p>

Once in operation at local/regional level, the Food Region CoP supports multi-actor, value chain co-creation and innovation in several ways and provides multiple societal benefits. **Attachment 1** provides an illustration of the agricultural landscape as a visualized objective of the process with some of the identified functions explained⁴.

⁴ Poster presented at Carbon Farming Summit 2026.

4. From concept to sustainable programmes

4.1 Operationalization of multi-stakeholder collaboration

This chapter identifies opportunities and good practices in operationalizing territorial and value chain level multi-actor collaboration, outlines features which contribute to their sustainability, and suggests systematic connection at EU level, utilizing EU level platforms and networks to multiply the value from individual initiatives.

Transforming Living Lab concepts and multi-actor collaboration (e.g. from Living Labs, EIP AGRI Operational Groups) into sustainable, long-term programmes requires a fundamental shift from project-based experimentation toward structured, institutionalized programmes, and adopting a systems orientation. While different project initiatives (see i.a. Attachment 3) demonstrate the feasibility of co-creation, real-life testing and cross-border exchange, their long-term impact depends on how effectively multi-actor approaches are operationalized, integrated in governance structures, and connected across Europe (Soil-X-Change 2025).

Operationalizing multi-stakeholder collaboration means translating the Multi-Actor-Approach (MAA) from a conceptual principle into structured, repeatable and manageable processes. This document defines effective multi-actor collaboration as a dynamic process built around cycles of co-creation, testing and reflection, with stakeholder engagement, ownership and participation. Within this context, Living Labs and EIP-AGRI OGs collaboration is beyond simple stakeholder participation and needs to be translated into structured co-creation systems. This requires a clear definition of roles among key actors including farmers, advisors, researchers, facilitators and policy stakeholders. Collaboration must rely on formalized interaction formats such as workshops, farm demonstrations and cross-visits, which create space for meaningful exchange and joint learning. Feedback mechanisms ensure that knowledge generated in practice is captured, reflected upon and reintegrated into further activities. In the agri-food space, integrating multi-actor approach within Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) is essential. By linking advisory services, research institutions and policy frameworks, AKIS provides the enabling infrastructure that allows collaboration to move beyond project boundaries. These structures ensure that collaboration is not temporary but remains over time and it is coordinated across actors and regions and contributes to broader national and European objectives (Soil-X-Change 2025).

4.1.1 Standardizing collaborative processes and building functional systems

A key step toward scaling multi-stakeholder collaboration is the standardization of methodologies. This includes harmonizing approaches to demonstration design and facilitation, stakeholder engagement formats, as well as monitoring and feedback collection. In practice, this means that activities such as farm demonstrations are no longer ad hoc events but are operationalized as co-designed learning processes integrated within Living Lab cycles and systematically documented to generate transferable knowledge. Such standardization enables comparability of results across regions, supports the accumulation of evidence over time, and allows successful approaches to be replicated in different agroecological and socio-economic contexts. Here it is important to distinguish comparability and transfer of results from the intercomparison of Living Labs as such, for which a common evaluation framework has been developed (DG AGRI 2026, SOILL). At the same time, operational collaboration depends on ensuring continuous knowledge flows which integrate farmer insights into analytical processes such as cost–benefit assessments, and the transformation of field results into dissemination outputs such as fact sheets, practice abstracts or audiovisual materials. In this way, collaboration evolves into a dynamic knowledge ecosystem rather than a series of isolated knowledge exchange events.

4.1.2 Financing long-term 'food region' collaboration

The values added from the coordinated systematic region/landscape scale collaboration materialize from the local ecosystem that serves as an innovation structure to serve the innovation and development needs of different sectors. As presented above, such collaboration has the potential also to attract sustained funding from a wide range of sources. On the other hand, informal collaboration platforms with strong thematic and functional connection and complementarity can leverage different types of funding (from private donors and public programmes) which facilitates exploiting synergies and delivers benefits for each client and objective more efficiently.

Yet, when the objective is to both i) sustain the coordinated territorial collaboration in short-to-medium term, and ii) to demonstrate and accelerate transition to climate-smart agriculture and food system, the CoP's must plan finance strategically and consider establishing and investing in specific structures which, depending on the strategy, aim to attract external investment capital or rely on increasing capital flow in the food ecosystem and redistributing that in a sustainable way. Proponents of regenerative agriculture (i.a.

EARA 2025, van Gerner) remind that in the current governance system, individual farmers carry most of the transition risk and have little incentives to accept the risk (for instance in anticipation of a reward). Therefore, financially viable or investable transition strategies (affecting primary production) must distribute transition risk structurally in the system, in other words, align the incentive across the capital and the farmers in a way which rewards long-term stewardship due to its impact on system sustainability and resilience (see **Table 3** above). Coordinating this in a local territorial context increases the likelihood of attracting local private capital (for i.a. investments, carbon certificates) and offers access to the knowledge and experience to help utilize public funding programmes in line with regional and local strategies and priorities. Systemic solutions, contributing to local development goals may thus be more conducive to blended funding schemes where government funds are used to kick off transition measures and provide security to overcome the early-stage transition period. From the standpoint of advancing the CRCF, embedding CF agenda in broader, more comprehensive regional and landscape level systems allow CF and CRCF strategies to emerge through a more broad-based analysis of the development needs and opportunities in the local agricultural and land use system. This would help design more viable CF programmes and scale up the projects to cover 500+ or 1000+ hectares to increase demand and improve the cost-efficiency and economic reasoning for all parties involved. Furthermore, embedding CRCF projects in longer-term territorial strategies would minimize the risk of opt-outs and reversals and support further on-boarding and continuity.

On this basis three financing strategies emerge. The first one rests on better coordination and complementarity with publicly funded programs, the second one taps into the agricultural supply chain's leading role whereas the third one combines local value system with capital investment. These are outlined below and summarized in **Table 4**. Practical recommendations on financing sustainability of the CoPs, specifically, through EU funding are given 4.2.

Strategy 1: Public funding to pave the way

The EU budget allocates significant amounts of public funds to agriculture and rural areas through the CAP (31% of EU budget; DG AGRI, EC, ECA 2024) and cohesion programmes. The European Court of Auditors (2024, 2021) has repeatedly criticized the CAP plans and CAP implementation for not sufficiently integrating funding and measures in agriculture with regional objectives (environment, climate, social, sustainability),

adding also specific needs to improve the impact of the EIP instrument (ECA 2026). The future EU budget, however, is expected to steer towards more integrated and coordinated strategies in the rural regions connecting agriculture, forestry, rural communities and economy, i.a. through the National and Regional Partnership Plans proposed as a key feature in the EU Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF) for the 2028-2034 period (EC 2025). In parallel, the CRCF offers a new and concrete mechanism to put economic value on land use and land management measures and to attract new private capital to invest in these measures alongside public funding. Urban municipalities are increasingly frontrunners in climate mitigation and climate adaptation and similarly rural municipalities or municipalities with extensive rural or agricultural areas are recognizing the potential the rural lands hold for the municipal climate and sustainability strategies and the terms regenerative farming and carbon farming are starting to appear in municipal strategies. There is thus a strong case for regional and municipal governments in agricultural regions to identify the connections between climate strategies, land use and the food system and to tap into the opportunities by aligning public funding programmes. Governments could also advance CF and CRCF certification programmes, schemes and projects, with different strategies, starting from strengthening the AKIS and advisory services to establishing MRV capacities and actively supporting scheme and project development (Credible 2025, ILVO). There is also emerging attention as well as practical support to gearing public funding to support sustainability and investments in Living Labs (PREPSOIL, DG AGRI 2026). Furthermore, governments can support linking territorial CF and bottom-up initiatives with regional agri-food clusters (such as Wagralim in Wallonia, Belgium, <https://www.wagralim.be/en/>) and build food system models which rely on sustainable land use and land management.

Strategy 2: Onboarding private market actors

Food industry and the market are turning attention to sourcing strategies to improve sourcing security, climate performance and climate-related financial risk mitigation (see **Table 3**). The emerging criteria frameworks (SAI Platform frameworks, regenerative farming criteria by different companies such as Nestlé, Carlsberg, Danone) and the landscape level schemes discussed above (LENs, EIT FOOD Landscapes). However, sustainable transition initiatives are balanced along the supply chain and involve farmers as equal business partners (i.a. Granholm et al 2022). Strengthening farmers' and producers' organisation and coordinated action is both a precondition for recognition of the farmers' role as well as a lever to strengthen the farmer's position in the collaboration, with the aim of leading, for instance, to both fair and dynamic contract terms (i.a. IEEP 2022). Similarly, to share benefits evenly and to maximize value from public funds and

publicly funded infrastructure and capacities (such as data and research), the implementing structures should be connected to a public entity with aligned interest and strategy. Coordinated actions with outcome-orientation and metrics, verified for sustainability through integration in farm management strategies and local value chains provide a favourable test bed for innovating blended finance solutions, one form of which is performance-based incentives and payment schemes, hence providing additional justification for government involvement. Governments, in this case, have the key role in connecting donors and public funding institutions and establishing blended schemes for the initiative. Blended schemes can be in the form of guarantees, risk-sharing arrangements and bridge funding with the aim of establishing private sector market for the desired objective and activity (i.a. Deloitte 2025). Involving farmers as business partners to smoothen transition and share risks and rewards may necessitate and lead to new structures and new forms of ownership.

Strategy 3: Investment case based on the local agri-food system

Attracting capital investments on a medium-to-long term cycle (5-to-10+ years) would be a gamechanger for local food systems. This would help to stay on the chosen path, leverage additional funding, allocate public funding for incremental purposes and build capacity and structures to orchestrate and administer the financial base in a systematic way, building partnerships with local banks and financiers. Lessons from the global food sustainability programmes and the voluntary carbon market finance sector indicate that in addition to return, investors seek big scale projects with real impact measured by the metrics available. As the metrics, and the finance sector logic currently aligns with scale and global attributes, there is little investment case in local small-scale projects and incremental improvements in, say, management practices. While there are promising signals that local level projects can attract local banks, investors and other private capital, through e.g. local banks partnering with municipalities and local actors in projects, examples of upscaling are scarce.

An alternative scaling strategy is to scale the local action to the systems level, establishing locally tailored value systems which could support new types of business models and thereby build investment cases for big capital. Comprehensive regional programs would, for instance, have stronger likelihood of creating value added for the investment, than, for instance investments in agricultural land, which, in Europe, is not responsive to land management improvements and it is hard to establish a business model in which farmers would earn purely on land quality improvements, as, for instance, experience with the

Dutch Farmland Fund confirms (a.s.r. real assets). As noted above, land scarcity and heavy subsidies drive land prices more than agronomic quality. Instead of aiming to make land management improvements investable, local agri-food stakeholders could seek to build business models that gain their competitive edge from particular local attributes, opportunities, conditions or business ecosystems and that can support new business models utilizing, for instance, advanced digitalization and data management or particularly well streamlined value chains and co-operation between the AKIS, the industry and the public bodies.

Local food region collaboration geared to produce an investment case is also the approach that best exhibits features that increase its EU-wide value such as strong farmer involvement, common definition of objectives, common approach to data basis for assessing outcomes and availability of needed local datasets locally (see further e.g. PREPSOIL). As an example, the Place Finance Lab, an operative concept designed by the Climate KIC, is piloting a comprehensive cross-sector model combining local value chains, data management business models and external investment. The Place Finance Lab is intended for a short-to-medium term intervention tailored to local value systems and development needs and opportunities combining economic, social and environmental attributes. As financing models, the concept combines value chain optimization, monetization of data and capital investment through impact bonds and equity investments in new entities (Climate KIC 2026).

Table 4. Overall outline of financing approaches for Food Region CoPs

Strategy type	Implementation, key structures * Key actors * Key measures	Potential outcomes supporting sustainable funding strategy
Public driven	Public policies and programmes, structures (CAP, territorial funds, research and innovation) *	More value for CAP and territorial funds; regional carbon market

	<p>AKIS, regions, municipalities, national government, public development companies</p> <p>*</p> <p>Programme alignment, territorial differentiation and prioritisation, local and regional branding</p>	
<p>Private and market driven</p>	<p>Food industry collaboration, external funding</p> <p>*</p> <p>Food processors, agricultural off-takers, farmers' organisations, producer cooperatives, ministries and other public bodies, dedicated process/project owner/manager</p> <p>*</p> <p>Integrating farming and sourcing strategies, farmer/producer cooperation and organisation, data management and sharing</p>	<p>Blended financing arrangements; stronger, self-sustaining, climate-proof local/regional supply chains</p>
<p>Capital investment conducive</p>	<p>Systematic multi-year project, local engagement and ownership, external funding</p> <p>*</p> <p>Core local agri-food value system stakeholders, AKIS and other research and innovation communities, data governance and management actors, local public bodies, data users, finance sector, dedicated process/project owner/manager</p> <p>*</p> <p>local analysis, engagement, ownership; strong vision and plan built on local needs, objectives and capacities, operationalizable business and revenue model, public guarantees, risk diversification, ESG value, potential increased farm income, carbon market potential</p>	<p>Food regions attract global risk capital</p>

4.2 Multiply value through systematic connection at EU level

While multi-stakeholder collaboration is anchored at the local level its full value emerges only when initiatives are effectively interconnected across Europe. The challenge at EU level is therefore not the lack of activities but their fragmentation. As paraphrased in Carbon Farming Summit 2026, we need to move beyond isolated pilots to "scaling ecosystems, not practices". This implies a transition from fragmented projects and local Living Labs toward coordinated, interoperable networks. Such connectivity is achieved by linking key components of the innovation landscape, including LLs, OGs, MRV platforms, certification schemes and EU knowledge infrastructures, as interconnected parts of a broader system that enables knowledge exchange, validation and scaling across regions, with capacity to adapt to regional specifics which has been an underlying objective in CREDIBLE.

The AKIS plays a critical role in structuring these connections. By linking CAP instruments with Horizon Europe projects, embedding innovations into advisory systems and aligning national and EU priorities, AKIS provides the institutional backbone necessary for scaling. In parallel, EU level digital platforms and repositories, such as the EIP-AGRI database or EU-FarmBook, function as key enablers by providing centralized access to knowledge, increasing visibility of practices and facilitating matchmaking between actors. Together, these elements provide for the digital and organizational infrastructure of European agri-innovation ecosystems. Furthermore, the food industry and value system networks and platforms at the EU level are largely separate from the AKIS and research community networks. Therefore, no existing network can facilitate these collaborative values-added to their full potential, but an active approach to building connections between the networks is needed. **This is where the Food Region Communities-of-Practice serve as regional hubs and environments in which the various connecting themes manifest in practice.**

"Data, transparency and data-sharing protocols are key building blocks in carbon farming & regenerative farming transition"

Digi4CSA-project

A crucial emerging pillar of EU level connectivity is data infrastructure. As discussed in the summit, future systems must enable interoperability between farm level data, corporate sustainability frameworks and policy reporting requirements. Different actors require different levels of data - from field and farm level to product and value chain level, making robust and trusted data governance essential. The principle of "collect once, use multiple

times” becomes central, allowing data generated by farmers to serve multiple purposes, including certification, corporate reporting and policy monitoring, while reducing duplication and transaction costs.

Ideally, the Communities of Practice will enable direct, transparent comparison and transferability of practices and results and support peer-to-peer learning and foster long-term relationship, knowledge accumulation and tailored innovation. These supports maximising the potential local and wider EU value from the communities of practice. Stakeholder experience in local cluster collaboration surfaces the following good practices and features to maximize EU value added of MAA (i.a. Soil-X-Change 2025):

- ✓ cross-border exchange through cross-visits and structures for transnational collaboration
- ✓ clustering LLs and OGs around shared challenges, such as soil health or carbon sequestration
- ✓ transparency and systematic approach to data and streamlining of metrics, local datasets and the MRV systems applied (whereas MRV could be understood to include monitoring for CRCF certification, performance against industry sustainability frameworks or metrics for impact bonds etc.)
- ✓ supporting organic formation of networks with parallel scale projects and utilizing these to apply for more impactful EU projects

Through open-ended non-exhaustive mapping, we have identified several EU platforms which are relevant and geared to support territorial cluster collaboration and uptake of learnings and results (**Table 5**). Among these are the MISSIONS, in particular Mission Soil and Mission Climate, EIP AGRI, the CAP Network, ERRIN network of regions.

Table 5. Key values of selected EU collaboration structures for Food Region CoPs

EU structure	Relevant potential value
EU CAP Network	Maintain database of projects and facilitating thematic connections (living lab attributes, topics covered by living labs) and showcasing successful HE projects, also to inspire new EIP OG's (see i.a. DG AGRI 2026)
EIP	EIP AGRI Operational Groups can convene AKIS actors for MAA (multi-actor partnerships) and are distinctively bottom-up collaborations. They are handicapped in terms of scale-up and transfer both due to specific local focus and shortage of funding for scaling and sustainability. Better information exchange and network connections between research, LL projects, national CAP networks and with related EIP's (such as

	water), as well as MS integration and promotion of LL and OG results in their AKIS, could help emerge more sustainable and higher EU-value OGs (i.a. DG AGRI 2026)
EIT	EIT FOOD can support landscapes, but as such, they are dependent on the local project design and ownership within the EIT FOOD programme boundaries. In addition, EIT FOOD collaborative mission programmes aim to connect multiple stakeholders for a systemic approach. EIT food is open to broaden the activities under its programmes with connected and joint funding / co-resourcing with other funders, NGO's, charities. This could lead e.g. to delivering living labs and structures to facilitate establishment of living labs (EIT FOOD collaborative missions). EIT FOODs main offer to programme implementers is to complement their capacities in grant management public engagement, community management and public affairs.
European funds for rural areas	Alignment of research, innovation, territorial development and specialization actions for food system transition would be facilitated by more systematic, integrated and complementary use of EU funds, topping-up MS regional funds (see i.a. ERRIN 2025a)
ERRIN	The European Regions Research and Innovation Network, errin.eu , convenes regional public entities which are essential to support Food Region CoP's. Currently, the working themes of ERRIN do not cover agriculture or the food system, but work in related areas, such as water, climate and circular economy could open connections between the food system and regional research and innovation.
Horizon Europe Missions	As an example, synergies between HE LL projects and the EIP AGRI OGs to contribute to future CAP, research and competitiveness policy and funds are mapped within HE Mission Soil. The initial mapping identifies that connected implementation and assessment of LL and OG results could facilitate evaluation of effectiveness of solutions and their uptake and upscaling potential. Raising the outputs from these activities to national and EU level consideration helps contribution to and alignment of policy and facilitation of funding to sustain high-value activities and approaches. Connecting OG's and LL projects through improved dissemination and communication is important for knowledge adoption, innovation and impactful outcomes (DG AGRI 2026).
Horizon Europe Partnerships	Participatory place-based or territorial approaches and action is a key focus in e.g. the Agroecology Partnership and the Food Systems Partnership . For impact and scalability of results, the partnerships would need to be supported by complementary action and funding, and strengthened, in particular, in terms of engagement of regional and local authorities and other stakeholders for broader support through the regional ecosystem. This could be facilitated through regional and national co-funding (Errin 2025a), which becomes a relevant consideration with the National and Regional Partnership Plans, in which discussions the regional authorities will have a stronger role than before.

LIFE	The LIFE instrument is a critical complementary funding instrument facilitating green transition and ecosystem restoration in which local and regional authorities often have a vested interest and active role in implementation (i.a. Errin 2025b). Therefore, it has high value also for food region CoP's from the perspective of adapting primary production to the ecological boundaries and implementing integrated strategies and measures.
EU Regional Partnerships	Specific regional partnerships with " <i>national governments, NGOs, and agricultural advisory services</i> " (Deloitte 2025) can be aligned with the NRPPs' to "embed a genuinely place-based approach", implement LL and OG results and strengthen and connect territorial R&I ecosystems (Errin 2025c, DG AGRI 2026). This could help deliver both regionally multi-beneficial CF projects as well as greater impact extending to the economies more broadly Europe-wide.

For additional platforms and projects advancing place-based and territorial multi-actor approach linked to the food system, please see **Attachment 3**.

4.2.1 EU programmes, policy and budget

Ultimately, EU programmes and policy have the power to leverage and steer transition in the agrifood systems. Essentially, this concept paper outlines approaches to learning in systems and governance. Indeed, the value of more strategic and systematic approach to policy process design and deployment of EU structures and programmes to accelerate policy and cumulative learning has been noted in i.a. CAP evaluations (i.a. Aakkula et al 2006). Too often, learning through examples is only an objective and a "wish", rather than a function embedded in how policy processes and their implementation is designed and how collaborative programmes are geared to support that in a transparent way. Generally, we cannot be stuck in isolated projects, pilots, policy silos and single target group orientation, but instead seize the momentum, shared sense of urgency and existing collaborative structures for institutional adaptation, replication and collective systems learning. European projects are expected to generate impact persistently struggle with the challenge of connecting with the decision-makers and processes that would most benefit from the project outputs and results. Projects produce results and tools which are designed to serve policy and systemic development, but validation of these tools and results require exposure to the real systemic and policy processes they are designed to serve.

In parallel, stronger regulatory incentives for transition through the food chain are needed (i.a. IEEP 2022), particularly, in consideration of the voids left by the abandoned EU Sustainable Food Systems Initiative and uncertainty with respect to the transitional

ambition of the corporate sustainability framework (see Iozzelli 2025). Supporting local and regional multi-actor agri-food collaborations could provide also politically more viable paths to meeting multiple objectives through bottom-up initiative.

The EU MFF for 2028-2034 will see significant structural changes, in particular with respect to merging the agricultural and cohesion funds into a single fund. The National and Regional Partnership Plans will present an impetus to design integrated strategies for the rural regions, necessitating further alignment of agricultural, rural development and sustainability strategies. Considering the political priority of competitiveness, integrating competitiveness and regional economies and embedding territorial multi-actor innovation and co-creation platforms could boost impact-oriented innovation and demonstrate how agriculture and local and regional value chains can be drivers of European competitiveness (i.a. Errin 2025b).

5. Accelerate roll-out as platforms for policy dialogue

A design approach for the CoP's anchored in regional and municipal strategies, aligning food systems, land use and climate resilience and addressing critical issues for the regional stakeholders and policymakers would make the initiative policy relevant and open a communication space and agenda for policy- and policy-maker dialogue. Involving regional value chains in the agenda setting and co-creation further reinforces the relevance from local decision-maker standpoint. Setting the objective to attract investment should also attract policymakers' interest in the CoP. Assuming relevance, policy-maker interest (mapping policy-makers and policy and political dynamics as part of the CoP strategy and design would be a valuable preparatory activity) and capacity of the CoP actors to carry out systematic policy dialogue, and, basing on learnings and successful examples, we outline below ways and actions for driving impactful policy dialogue anchored in the territorial CoPs.

Table 6. Measures to engage decision-makers and advance policy dialogue

Level: strategic / tactic	Activity	Main level: national / EU
strategic	Combination of field activities, co-creation, communication and advocacy in a multi-sector strategic advocacy strategy and plan which, in addition to advocacy and PA, includes building on-the-ground partnerships and supporter-base for the agenda and solutions.	national, EU
strategic	Due mapping of key actors, stakeholders and their motivations and inter-group dynamics. Identify decision-makers and backers to be targeted based on their power, interest and support for the agenda.	national, EU
strategic	Due mapping of relevant policies, implementation and transposition processes as well as longer term strategy and planning processes relevant for the territory and the multi-actor co-creation agenda.	national, EU
tactic	Communicating the agenda, partnership and stakeholder strategy of the territorial collaboration openly and in a targeted way to gain attention and recognition. Visioning positive outcomes that cater also to motivations other than science-based reasoning. Maintain continuous, open communication.	national
tactic	Attracting the passive stakeholders who support the agenda and could become interested backers and advocates of the agenda and the collaboration.	national
tactic	Physical meeting places, preferably in an environment exhibiting concrete action and solutions, convening practitioners, scientists, business	national

	representatives, interest representatives, authorities and politicians. Regular (bi-annual, annual) events with changing group composition to accumulate a large group of stakeholders and decision-makers exposed to the agenda and solution.	
tactic	Engaging key decision-makers at personal level with the agenda and individual "work streams" or solutions. Demonstration of the relevance of CoP agenda and solutions for these key decision-makers' home region, if they are from another region or country.	national, EU
tactic	Building internal policy dialogue and advocacy capacity in the CoP and deploy that regularly to sustain and strengthen that. Repeated, regular, targeted communication with relevant and targeted value added and make sure to deliver information when there is a need or a window for that, not when you have the information compiled and consensually validated.	national
tactic	Bringing practitioners and regional level stakeholders in personal contact with, especially, national and EU level policymakers.	national, EU
tactic	The solutions initially planned or even initial problem definition may not carry through the process, hence, patience and adaptive capacity is needed for true co-creation and collective learning to take place and shape the process and solutions. As an example, Ireland is applying the Deep demonstration methodology (Climate KIC, see Figure 1 below) in its national CF programme to execute a co-learning process. Yet, the process does aim to build commitment of policymakers by connecting the solutions and targeted values and benefits to the laws and commitments the policymakers ought to implement.	national

Figure 1. Climate KIC Deep demonstration model as an adaptive process framework for the Irish Carbon Farming Strategy (Department of Agriculture 2025)

As described above, the value of CoP's is in systems learning. This links to the element of social innovation in multi-actor approaches, transecting scientific and policy processes, not just "as an afterthought to technology" (Zirngiebl et al 2025). Therefore, the CoP's should be also appreciated for the potential value to support social innovation in how we collectively build understanding and transform our societies and economies. Social innovation in the CoP's can, for instance, contribute to discoveries in institutional structures or organisations that could facilitate new, more integrated approaches. Zirngiebl et al (2025) describe the value of social innovation and the untapped potential of EU Missions, including the Soil Health Living Labs, to support social innovation. Incorporating the social innovation aspect in the CoP's with dedicated expertise and research would also strengthen capacity for policy dialogue both in terms of expert capacities as well as broader societal and cross-sector relevance. This would make the CoP's the platforms with local collaborations, build trust between farmers and authorities and respond to the need of locally based policy learning.

6. References

Literature

1. Aakkula, J., P. Jokinen, M. Kaljonen & L. Kröger (2006): Maatalouden ympäristöpolitiikan skaalat ja oppiminen. MTT:n selvityksiä 127, <https://jukuri.luke.fi/server/api/core/bitstreams/1335e37e-5892-4f73-9e6f-947e6c9e45e4/content>
2. Berninger K., A. Perrels, P. Robinson, S. Saklani, L. Trentini & H. Gregow (2026): White paper for the insurance sector. D4.5 of PIISA-project, https://piisa-project.eu/assets/deliverables/PIISA_D4.5-White-paper-for-the-insurance-sector.pdf
3. Bucheli, J., N. Conrad, S. Wimer, T. Dalhaus & R. Finger (2023): Weather insurance in European crop and horticulture production, *Climate Risk Management* vol 41, 2023, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2212096323000517>
4. Carbon Action (2026): Collaboration for shared benefits. Experiences from value chain collaboration in regenerative agriculture. Presentation at Carbon Farming Summit 2026 by Kaj Granholm.
5. Cave, J., M. Botterman, S. Cavallini & M. Volpe (2017): EU-wide digital Once-Only Principle for citizens and businesses. Final report. European Commission DG Communications Networks, Content & Technology, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?doc_id=42300
6. Climate KIC (2026): Place Finance Lab. Collaborative Financial Innovation for Regional Food Systems. Introduction to the Lab and Excerpts from Regional Research Findings. March 2026.
7. CONSOLE (2022): Biodiversity monitor for DAIRY farming, https://console-project.eu/Nuevos_deliverables/NL3_fin_2022.pdf
8. CoR (2023): Regional adaptation strategies for low carbon agriculture. Opinion. 153rd plenary session, 8 and 9 February 2023, NAT-VII/027. Committee of the Regions.
9. Credible (2025): Fit-for-region blueprint for carbon scheme development. Deliverable 1.4 of the Credible-project.
10. Deeg, R. and Hardie, I. 2016: "What is patient capital and who supplies it?" *Socio-Economic Review* vol. 14, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ser/mww025>
11. Deloitte (2025): Support to the design of policy options for financial incentives for carbon farming. European Commission, July 2025.

12. Department of Agriculture (2025): Carbon Farming Developments at European Union level and draft Principles to develop Carbon Farming in Ireland, Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine, October 2025, https://assets.gov.ie/static/documents/a2782ad1/Dev_at_EU_level_and_draft_Principles_to_dev_Carbon_Farming_15_October_2025_Fi.pdf
13. DG AGRI (2026): 'Exploring potential synergies between Horizon Europe projects using living labs and lighthouses applied to agriculture, the Common Agricultural Policy EIP-AGRI Operational Group projects and other similar initiatives: the Mission Soil example', non-paper. Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development Unit F.2 Research and Innovation February 2026.
14. EARA (2025): Farmer-led Research on Europe's Full Productivity. European Alliance for Regenerative Agriculture, https://www.eara.farm/wp-content/uploads/EARA_Farmer-led-Research-on-Europes-Full-Productivity_2025_06_03.pdf
15. ECA (2021): Common Agricultural Policy and climate. Special Report 16/2021. European Court of Auditors.
16. ECA (2024): Common Agricultural Policy Plans. Special Report 20/2024. European Court of Auditors, https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/SR-2024-20/SR-2024-20_EN.pdf
17. ECA (2026): European innovation partnership in the common agricultural policy. Special Report 09/2026, https://www.eca.europa.eu/ECAPublications/SR-2026-09/SR-2026-09_EN.pdf
18. EEA (2024): European Climate Risk Assessment. EEA Report 01/2024. European Environment Agency, <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/european-climate-risk-assessment>
19. EESC (2025): Regenerative agriculture as a target towards enhancing sustainable food production. Opinion, NAT/948, European Economic and Social Committee.
20. ERRIN (2025a): ERRIN INPUT TO THE FUTURE HORIZON EUROPE (FP10), 7 November 2025, https://errin.eu/system/files/2025-11/251107%20ERRIN%20Horizon%20Europe%20input%20paper_0.pdf
21. ERRIN (2025b): ERRIN INPUT TO THE EUROPEAN COMPETITIVENESS FUND, 12 November 2025, https://errin.eu/system/files/2025-11/251112_ERRIN_European%20Competitiveness%20Fund%20input%20paper_0.pdf

22. Granholm, K., T. Kaarlamo & N. Wardi (2022): Shared value – an outlook on market driven environmental funding innovations in agriculture. Output 5.3 of the Waterdrive-project, <https://water-drive.eu/wp5-strategic-impact-and-environmental-investments/>
23. Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council (2026): Helsinki-Uusimaa, a Region of Solutions – Pioneer in Finland, Forerunner in Europe Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Programme 2026–2029, Publications of the Helsinki-Uusimaa Regional Council A 62 – 2026, <https://uudenmaanliitto.fi/wp-content/uploads/2026/02/Helsinki-Uusimaa-a-Region-of-Solutions.pdf>
24. IEEP (2022): Just transition in the EU agriculture and land use sector. Institute of European Environmental Policy.
25. Ingram, J. et al (2016) Communicating soil carbon science to farmers: Incorporating credibility, salience and legitimacy, Journal of Rural Studies vol 48, December 2016, DOI:10.1016/j.jrurstud.2016.10.005
26. LaCanne, C. & J. Lundgren (2018): Regenerative agriculture: merging farming and natural resource conservation profitably, PeerJ 6:e4428, <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.4428>
27. Soil-X-Change (2025): Fostering cross-border knowledge exchange and co-creation on sustainable soil and farm management: Deliverable 5.1 – How to build soil Living Lab including organization of farm demonstrations guide, HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01-18.
28. Stevens, A. (2022): The economics of land tenure and soil health, Soil Security 6 (2022) 100047, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soisec.2022.100047>
29. Svensk Kolinlagring (2025): Årsberättelse 2025, Svensk Kolinlagring AB, https://svenskkolinlagring.se/wp-content/uploads/2026/02/SK_Arsberattelse-2025.pdf
30. Vira, J., H. Vekuri, O. Nevalainen, M. Korkiakoski, T. Mattila, H. Aaltonen, M. Koskinen, A. Lohila, M. Pihlatie & J. Liski (2025): Improving agricultural carbon monitoring with Sentinel-2 and eddy-covariance-based plant productivity estimates, Carbon Management vol 16, 2025, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17583004.2025.2568042>
31. Zibecchi, Tiago, Forouheshfar, Yeganeh & Ayadi, Rym (2025): Systemic Financing for Regenerative Agriculture in Europe: Evidence from ReForest Living Labs, preprint, <https://doi.org/10.21203/rs.3.rs-7613055/v1>
32. Zimmer, D., S. Armstrong-Twigg & L. Trupp (2025a): 2nd European Carbon Farming Summit Report.

33. Zimmer, D., S. Pietosi, T. Bacchetti De Gregoris & S. Keesstra (2025b): Building credibility and value for Europe's carbon farming transition, Opinio paper.
<https://zenodo.org/records/17865504>
34. Zirngiebl, M., S. Beckers, W. Haider, J. Howaldt, E. NAmaganda, F. Schnecke & K. Schuch (2025): Social innovations in support of the EU-missions, Deliverable Nr 1.1. Social Innovation Mission Facility.

Online posts

1. de Wit, B. (2025): Sustainability-Linked Loan: Definition & How to obtain, blog, 29.4.2025, <https://www.regreener.earth/blog/sustainability-linked-loan-definition-how-to-obtain>
2. EC (2025): An ambitious budget for a stronger Europe: 2028-2034. Press release, July 2025, European Commission, https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_25_1847.
3. ERRIN (2025c): Errin's input on the Multiannual Financial Framework 2028-2034 proposals, 20 November 2025, <https://errin.eu/news/errins-input-multiannual-financial-framework-2028-2034-proposals>
4. Iozzelli, L. (2025): The Omnibus Simplification Package Proposal: A Test of the EU's Unity, <https://www.greendealnet.eu/Omnibus-Simplification-Package-Proposal>.
5. IRISCC (2026): Bringing Stakeholders Together: Designing the Future of Carbon and Agricultural Data in Finland, iriscc.eu, 30.3.2026.
6. Liski, J. (2025): "Monitoring Carbon Sequestration in Agricultural Fields", 27.2.2025, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s47KimbGmRg>
7. Tchoukanov, S. (2025): Why Europe's regenerative agriculture needs clearer rules and faster action, Euractiv, 17 December 2025, <https://www.euractiv.com/opinion/why-europes-regenerative-agriculture-needs-clearer-rules-and-faster-action/>
8. van Gerner, 2026: <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/47-biggest-risk-regenerative-agriculture-structural-lg7se/> , Angelique van Gerner, January 26 2026.

Websites

- AlVelAl, <https://landscapes.global/partnership/alvelal/>
a.s.r. real assets, <https://en.asrealestate.nl/investments/asr-dutch-farmland-fund>

CAP Network, https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/support/innovation-knowledge-exchange-eip-agri/akis_en, https://eu-cap-network.ec.europa.eu/operational-groups_en

Digi4CSA, <https://www.bsag.fi/en/projects/digi4csa/>

DG AGRI, https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/common-agricultural-policy/cap-overview/cap-glance_en

EC, https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/long-term-eu-budget/2021-2027/whats-new_en#revision-of-the-eu-budget-2021-2027

ICMA, International Capital Market Association, The Sustainability-Linked Bonds Principles, Illustrative KPIs Registry, <https://www.icmagroup.org/sustainable-finance/the-principles-guidelines-and-handbooks/sustainability-linked-bond-principles-slbp/>

ILVO, <https://ilvo.vlaanderen.be/en/news/flanders-tackles-climate-change-with-carbon-removal-and-carbon-farming>

JRC, <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/jrc/communities-of-practice-playbook/en/>

SAI Platform, <https://saiplatform.org/regenerating-together-programme/>

PREPSOIL, <https://prepsoil.eu/living-labs-and-lighthouses/business-model-canvas-overview>

Personal communication

Personal communication (K. Granholm) with undisclosed finance sector representatives during autumn 2025-winter 2026.

Attachment 1: Green field landscapes as a concept envisioning selected outcomes of the CoP approach

GREEN FIELD LANDSCAPES for RESILIENT FOOD SYSTEMS and CARBON SEQUESTRATION

Carbon Action MRV

This state-of-the-art MRV system allows parcel-level carbon balance estimates and carbon-removal accounting according to IPCC Tier 3 guidelines and the **CRCF** framework. It links satellite-based plant growth estimates with soil carbon calculations using the Yasso model, and incorporates farm data on harvests, yields and organic inputs.

Video introducing the system

Incentives

Incentivizing green cover in space and time increases resilience at both farm and system-level. Incorporating outcome-based payments enables flexibility and context-specific adaptive management. The pilot concept will explore possibilities of outcome-based incentives in the **CAP**, and the potential for **CRCF**-certified removals.

Information

Benefits for all

- Improved water quality
- Resilience and security in food production
- Food sovereignty
- Reduced dependence on imported inputs

Local development
Wellbeing of rural communities

Generational continuity
Improving economy

Biodiversity

Adding as few as 1-2 additional plant species (e.g. undersown crops) increases soil carbon inputs, and reduces plant diseases and insect pests. Tailored carbon farming practices can increase biodiversity.

Carbon uptake

Photosynthesis, $gC/m^2 \text{ day}$

Cover crops can increase the annual carbon uptake by 15% via photosynthesis during the autumn months.

Adding leys into the crop rotation increases carbon uptake effectively.

2021

GDP mean

1400

800

0

Multi-year ley
Ley rotation
Autumn sown
Annual

Soil fertility

Improved soil health increases yield reliability while reducing the need for fertilisers. For example, cover crops and leys increase plant-available nitrogen in the soil.

PILOT CONCEPT

We present a pilot concept testing gross primary productivity (GPP) as an indicator for a result-based **CAP** payment model in arable crop systems.

This pilot concept focuses on soil carbon due to the multi-functional linkages between soil health, food production, and other ecosystem services. Plant photosynthesis is the main pathway for carbon input to soils, and can be maximised by extending green vegetative cover in time and space by including e.g. leys and undersown crops in cropping cycles.

GPP can be derived from satellite data. In this pilot concept, we will use the highly accurate **GPP** estimates produced by the Carbon Action MRV. Furthermore, this state-of-the-art MRV system allows parcel-level carbon balance estimates and carbon-removal accounting according to IPCC Tier 3 guidelines and the **CRCF** framework.

The pilot explores how this type of payment can be established in fair and effective ways. The concept further creates possibilities to develop complementarity across **CAP** and market-based incentives. The concept can be utilized in existing landscape studies where farmers are involved.

References

Vira et al. 2025, Carbon Manag.
Mattila et al. 2025, Eur. J. Agron.
Susi et al. 2026, Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.
Cappelli et al. 2022, Trends Plant Sci.
Mattila et al. 2023, Soil Use Manag.

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Attachment 2: Concept for a systemic pilot to develop result-based CAP-measures aligned with the CRCF

Through the Carbon Farming Summits and Credible dialogues, the farmers' representatives have maintained the need to adapt farm level strategies in a holistic way, to strengthen the preconditions of productive agriculture. Cultivation practises that build resilience and soil health often align with soil carbon sequestration, and thus the two objectives can be combined. For the CAP, result-based payments are increasingly being advocated by administration and farmers to increase effectiveness of policy (often motivation for the former group) and flexibility at farm level (motivation for the latter group). But soil carbon as the indicator for result-based payments - does not optimally capture the farm management benefits nor does it fully align with farm level sustainability objectives. The Finnish Carbon Action collaboration, drawing from its experience in studying CF practises on 100 pilot farms and contributing i.a. to the EARA study (2025), has put forth a policy pilot concept which tests the feasibility of result-based CAP-payments aligned with CF objectives. Specifically, this proposes to use Gross (or Net) Primary Productivity as an indicator for carbon sequestration with multiple benefits and thereby as an indicator for a result-based CAP payment. The data for the indicator would be drawn from publicly available data sources and converted to GPP/NPP. This value is then compared to a regional and production system-normalized baseline. It is important to acknowledge that here the GPP is not intended as a direct proxy indicator for soil carbon stock increase. Similarly, the sustained soil carbon stock increase is not the KPI for this measure, but rather increased vegetative cover, which consequently could yield favourable results in GHG inventory as well as, in concrete ways result in higher biodiversity and reduced water erosion as described below.

The GPP/NPP as a target is expected to lead to increase of green vegetation in time (as days over a year/cropping cycle) and space (as arable hectares) through, e.g. addition/increase of undersown crops, cover crops, winter crops, legumes, green manuring or grazing, including switching to rotational grazing. In addition to increasing carbon sequestration in the soil through increased photosynthesis, depending on the agricultural system in which - and how - they are applied, these practises are expected to improve soil structure, reduce soil erosion, increase water infiltration and soil's water holding capacity, increase biodiversity below and above ground, increase farm systems resistance to diseases and pests and thereby reducing the need for chemical pesticides and herbicides as well as reduce the need for mineral fertilization.

The incentive payment is calculated considering specific regional objectives, other available incentive schemes and safeguards to avoid unwanted market disturbances. These considerations justify the development of this policy measure through piloting. On the other hand, the territorial delineation of the pilot would help in communication, provision of advisory support to farmers as well as observing (monitoring) the co-benefits such as water quality improvements and biodiversity recovery. The pilot can be designed to run for only one or for multiple years.

Monitoring and incentivizing based on a few key outcome metrics is increasingly also the preferred approach by the food and finance sector to advance sustainability. This is proven by stakeholder workshops carried out within the Carbon Action collaboration as well as the keynotes and discussions in the recent Carbon Farming Summit. The pilot would also help establish complementarity across the CAP and the CRCF. In this approach, additional carbon sequestration to qualify for CRCF certification would be accounted separately with additional farm level data on yields and carbon inputs and compared to a standardized or a project-based baseline.

The Food Region Communities of Practice would provide an operational, controllable, real-world context to innovate and pilot policy measures in collaboration with farmers, the AKIS and the value chain and tailor measures which would be more efficient from the perspective of using public funds and which would be better in line with farm and the food industry strategies. Taking into consideration, for instance, that different reporting frameworks require carbon/GHG data at different scales (different resolutions and time spans, area vs product based), using the CoPs for this type of policy piloting would facilitate learning also about data sourcing, data sharing and joint data management across reporting frameworks (CAP, CRCF, GHG Protocol Scope 3, national inventories) as well as about operationalizing MRV for CRCF. **Figure 2** below illustrates calculation of GPP and soil carbon sequestration with the Carbon Action MRV developed by the Finnish Meteorological Institute (Vira et al 2025, Liski).

Figure 2. Calculation of GPP and soil carbon sequestration. Graphics by Nuria Altimir. See more about the pilot concept, the MRV and the expected benefits in **Attachment 1**.

Attachment 3: List of platforms and projects relevant to territorial multi-actor approach in primary production systems or value chains

This non-exhaustive list is intended as further aid to facilitate new connections and exchange between the reader and stakeholders working with similar topics.

Platforms, programmes, EU Preparatory action

- European Cluster Collaboration Platform (ECCP), www.clustercollaboration.eu
- Innovation for place-based transformation, place-based-innovation.ec.europa.eu/projects-0/preparatory-action-2024-2026_en
- Large-scale pilots, digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/activities/digital-programme
- Regional Innovation Valleys, research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/support-policy-making/shaping-eu-research-and-innovation-policy/new-european-innovation-agenda/roadmap/flagship-3-accelerating-and-strengthening-innovation-european-innovation-ecosystems-across-eu-and/regional-innovation-valleys_en
- SOILL 2030 database, soill2030.app/groups

Projects and private initiatives

- Adaptation Hubs, errin.eu/projects/adaptationhubs
- AQUAGRI-KNOW, aquagri-know.eu
- BBioNets, bbionets.eu
- Carbon Action, carbonaction.org
- Carboneg, carboneg.com
- Carbonica, carbonica-hub.eu
- Commonland, <https://commonland.com/landscapes/reversing-desertification-with-regenerative-practices/>
- Landscape Enterprise Networks, <https://landscapeenterprisenetworks.com/>
- Pathways-2-Resilience, www.pathways2resilience.eu
- Regilience+, regilience.eu
- Resist, resist-project.eu
- SOILL, SOILL-stepup soill2030.eu
- Soil-X-Change, soil-x-change.eu

CREDIBLE
EU carbon farming